

Knowledge Extraction in the Age of LLMs

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In recent years, instruction-tuned **Large Language Models (LLMs)** have emerged as a powerful tool for text analysis. These models can perform annotation tasks based on natural language instructions—known as prompts—eliminating the need for extensive manually labeled training data (Wei et al., 2022). Their versatility makes them valuable for a wide range of text-based applications, from common tasks like sentiment analysis and topic modeling to more specialized annotation challenges. Unlike earlier methods that primarily rely on syntactic patterns, LLMs leverage contextual understanding and inference, enabling them to achieve high performance across languages—sometimes even matching human experts in annotation tasks (Törnberg, 2024b).

Hierarchical text classification, which assigns documents to multiple categories within a structured label taxonomy, presents unique challenges for LLMs. **Large and complex label spaces make direct prompting ineffective**, leading to information loss, increased computational costs, and difficulty in distinguishing class-specific details. Most previous approaches rely on fully supervised (Chen et al., 2021) or semi-supervised learning methods (Gururangan et al., 2019), where models are trained on extensive human-labeled datasets. However, manual annotation is often expensive, time-consuming, and difficult to scale.

As part of the Horizon Europe EFRA research project, **we explore the innovative use of LLMs for knowledge extraction in Food Safety Incident Reports**. Our goal is to identify key pieces of information—such as hazards and affected products—and categorize them within a hierarchical multi-label classification (HMC) framework. This classification spans thousands of potential concepts drawn from publicly available ontologies that constitute the EFRA conceptual model.

Figure 1: Knowledge Extraction

The EFRA conceptual model aims to establish a shared representation of the key concepts and entities relevant to project use cases. Whenever possible, it links specific entities to publicly available ontologies, following the **Linked Open Data (LOD)** principle.

For our experiments, we used the public **Food Safety Incidents** dataset¹ from Agroknow (**AFSI**). Each incident report typically describes one or more food products affected by specific issues, such as contamination or mislabelling. These issues may involve particular substances or organic components that provide additional context within the broader category of food safety hazards.

The following diagram illustrates the top-level concepts relevant to our task and defines the key knowledge elements we aim to extract. Annotations based on these root concepts can be further refined and expanded by linking them to external ontologies.

Figure 2: EFRA Conceptual model and Food Safety Hazard Thesaurus

In the first year of the project, we conducted a comprehensive review of ontologies, thesauri, and dictionaries relevant to food risk assessment and safety. From this review, we selected a subset of resources based on their coverage of data in the AFSI dataset. The selected resources include:

- **AGROVOC²** – The FAO multilingual thesaurus, developed and maintained by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations. It is a controlled vocabulary that spans topics such as food, nutrition, agriculture, fisheries, forestry, and the environment. AGROVOC serves as a lexical and semantic resource for content annotation, information retrieval, data integration, and data mining. It contains over 40,000 concepts and is available in up to 29 languages.
- **FoodOn³** – An open-source, comprehensive ontology that structures food-related terminology. It includes hierarchies for raw food ingredients, processing terms (e.g., packaging, cooking, preservation), and product type classifications. FoodOn currently contains approximately 10,000 concepts, primarily expressed in English.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/10891602>
² <https://www.fao.org/agrovoc/>
³ <https://foodon.org/>

- **ChEBI⁴ (Chemical Entities of Biological Interest)** – A bioinformatics and cheminformatics ontology focused on molecular entities, particularly small chemical compounds. It captures relationships and properties of chemicals relevant to biological and biochemical contexts, with over 46,000 entries, primarily in English.
- **GS1GPC⁵ (Global Product Classification)** – A system that categorizes products within a four-level hierarchical structure: Segment, Family, Class, and Brick. The "Brick" level is particularly important, grouping products that share common purposes, forms, materials, and attributes. Unlike other resources, GS1 GPC provides rich contextual information, including detailed textual descriptions specifying inclusions and exclusions rather than just labels and synonyms. It contains over 180,000 Brick-level entries, primarily in English.

The resulting label space includes hundreds of thousands of concepts, making a direct prompting approach impractical. To address this, a mechanism is required to preselect a subset of relevant labels based on the specific information piece being classified or linked.

In our experiment, we explored a **Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG)-like entity linking approach**, inspired by the well-known RAG architecture. This method integrates a **Knowledge Base**, which includes all entries from the EFRA conceptual model, with a Search Engine that indexes these entities. When a fragment of information needs to be classified, the system queries the search engine to retrieve a list of potentially relevant entities or candidate labels. The LLM then processes this curated subset, leveraging the contextual information to select the most appropriate classification(s). This approach enhances efficiency by significantly reducing the number of labels the LLM needs to evaluate, improving both scalability and accuracy. It also ensures that entity selection is grounded in structured knowledge while allowing the model to retain flexibility in contextual interpretation.

We initially tested **our RAG-like entity linking** approach to map the textual representations of products mentioned in reports (e.g., organic tortilla chips) to the **GS1 GPC taxonomy**. Our search strategy employs a **hybrid retrieval mechanism**, combining tensor-based search (for semantic similarity) with **keyword search** (for exact matches). Encouraged by promising initial results, we extended this approach to cover the entire **EFRA conceptual model**, indexing and enriching the entries of all selected semantic resources. As a result, we developed a set of functions that allow us to obtain across all relevant knowledge sources, which are now available for further **candidate mappings** experimentation.

⁴ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/chebi/>

⁵ <https://gpc-browser.gs1.org/>

Figure 3: RAG-like Entity Linking

The next step in our experiments was integrating these search functions as **tools within an LLM agent**. An **LLM agent** is an AI system that extends the capabilities of a **Large Language Model (LLM)** by incorporating external tools, structured knowledge sources, and APIs. Unlike a standalone LLM, which passively generates responses to prompts, an LLM agent follows a structured workflow: it can reason, retrieve information dynamically (e.g., interacting with web APIs) and iterate on partial results to refine its outputs. This makes it particularly well-suited for complex tasks such as **question answering, data extraction, and workflow automation**.

In our specific use case, the **LLM agent** is tasked with:

1. Summarizing report contents – This step normalizes and minimizes variability across reports, ensuring consistent processing.
2. Identifying key entities – The agent extracts mentions of hazards and products from the text.
3. Retrieving candidate entities – Using the identified hazard and product mentions as inputs, the agent queries the search functions over the knowledge base (KB) to obtain a set of relevant candidate entities.
4. Selecting the most fitting entity – The LLM processes the retrieved candidates and determines the most appropriate classification(s).

To achieve this, the agent decomposes the task into a sequence of steps, executing each step iteratively while storing partial results in memory. These stored results are then used to draw final conclusions and generate the requested analysis as output.

A key takeaway from this architecture is that the **LLM itself is just one component of the system**, rather than the sole intelligence driving the process. This modular design allows for **flexibility in model selection**, meaning different LLMs can be plugged into the system depending on the task's requirements, performance considerations, or domain-specific needs.

Figure 4: Food Safety Hazard Thesaurus

Our **preliminary results** are encouraging, demonstrating that the proposed approach is effective for **Knowledge Extraction and Entity Linking** within large and complex label spaces. By leveraging a RAG-like retrieval mechanism and integrating LLM agents with structured knowledge bases, we have successfully mapped textual representations to relevant concepts across multiple ontologies. This approach enhances **scalability, accuracy, and interpretability** in classification tasks.

The following image illustrates the **analysis output** for an example document, showcasing how the system identifies key entities and links them to structured knowledge sources.

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Incidents Dataset Selected Report Analysis Explanation

SUMMARY

Batches of various brands of **Organic Tortilla Chips** are being recalled due to the possible presence of **Tropane alkaloids**, which are naturally occurring toxins. Adverse effects in humans can include changes in heart rate, decreased salivary and sweat secretion, pupil dilation, dizziness, headache, and nausea. Contamination can occur if parts of tropane alkaloid-containing plants are unintentionally harvested with agricultural crops.

HAZARD (*Tropane alkaloids*):

chemical hazard <http://www.efra.com/fsh/v1/ChemicalHazard>

RELATED CONCEPTS:

- tropane alkaloid http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CHEBI_37332*
- tropane http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CHEBI_35615*
- alkaloid http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CHEBI_22315*

PRODUCT (*Organic Tortilla Chips*):

Dressings/Dips (Perishable) <https://gpc-browser.gs1.org/?code=10000199>

RELATED CONCEPTS:

- tortilla chip http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/FOODON_03310710*
- tortilla http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/FOODON_03307668*
- organic molecule http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CHEBI_72695*

Select an LLM model

Analyze Selected Report

Figure 5: LLM agent analysis example

Building on these promising results, our **next steps** will focus on:

1. Integrating additional LLMs – Expanding the system to support multiple LLMs will allow us to compare performance across different models and optimize their use for specific tasks.
2. Creating a gold standard dataset – To systematically evaluate the effectiveness of various LLMs, we will develop a benchmark dataset with manually verified entity mappings. This will provide an objective basis for measuring accuracy, consistency, and robustness across different configurations.
3. Refining retrieval and classification strategies – We aim to enhance the hybrid search mechanism by fine-tuning the balance between semantic and keyword-based retrieval, improving precision in candidate selection.
4. Exploring adaptive learning techniques – Investigating methods to allow the system to continuously improve based on feedback and newly available data.

These advancements will further strengthen the **scalability and reliability** of our approach, paving the way for broader applications in **automated knowledge extraction, hierarchical classification, and AI-driven decision support**.

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